

Application of Skills and Performance Outcomes in Nigerian Public Service: Rethinking Elasticity Dynamics

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Abstract

This paper examines the relationship between skills application and performance outcomes in Nigerian public service through the lens of elasticity dynamics. It argues that performance responsiveness to skills utilization is neither linear nor uniform but varies according to organizational context, managerial practices, and institutional support. By re-conceptualizing skills–performance elasticity, the paper highlights threshold and diminishing-return effects that limit performance gains when skills are poorly aligned with roles or unsupported by enabling environments. The paper advances the position that effective performance improvement in the public service depends less on the volume of traditional-skills acquired and more on how strategically and consistently those digitally skills are applied. The paper contributes by offering a conceptual lens for re-thinking workforce development and presents actionable implications for policymakers, administrators, and human resource practitioners seeking continuous sustainable performance enhancement.

Keywords: skills application, performance outcomes, elasticity dynamics, public service.

Introduction

Public service is entrusted with the execution and implementation of policies, maintenance of government day-day operations; they provide solid foundation upon which societal yearnings, aspirations, dreams and visions are actualized (Ojo, 2023; PMS Policy, 2022). Developing the performance of employees is key in achieving organisational effectiveness and service delivery; thus necessitates systematic approach to training and development. Generally, organizations have vested interest in career development of their employees, as this enhances employee retention while simultaneously improving performance efficiency and effectiveness (Nwapi, 2023). From the early 2000s onward, organizations do invest more—not less—in initiatives for the purpose of retaining, training, and developing talent. In this regard, training serves as strategic tools through which organizations equip their workforce to achieve institutional goals and objectives. These efforts operate within the internal structure of public service, which consists of socio-technical arrangements deliberately designed to ensure that tasks are performed appropriately, timely, and in the right measure to achieve desired outcomes.

Building on this perspective, skills development is fundamental to the sustainability and survival of public service. Training is the primary source of skills development- several scholars have come up with different definitions of what training is all about; training implies improvement in overall effectiveness of the job; a systemic approach that utilises learning experiences to impart knowledge, cultivate skills and attitudes, and foster the growth of individuals or groups with the ultimate goal of enhancing performance (Ojo, 2023). In addition, training addresses employees' deficiencies (Vinesh, 2014). Improvement in skills, knowledge, and competence of a workforce is

non-negotiable as this is needed for a competitive advantage (Halawi and Hayday, 2018; Lin and Hsu, 2017 and Showkat et al 2023); understanding how skills correlates with performance provides valuable insights for human resource planning (Sadiya and Singh, 2025).

A well developed and effectively managed training framework can therefore deliver “the right people with the right skills at the right time to deliver overall objectives and outcome. Research indicates that well-structured training leads to improved service delivery, employee motivation, organisational commitment and higher productivity (Musa and Mohammed, 2023). Productivity is generally understood as the capacity to perform work-related tasks in line with predetermined standards, measured in terms of speed, cost efficiency, accuracy, and completeness (Sultana, Irum, Ahmed, & Mehmood, 2012). From economist view, the International Labour Organization conceptualizes productivity as the ratio between outputs and the inputs of resources utilized in the production process (Kato, 2016). At the employee level, productivity is closely associated with individual’s ability to complete assigned tasks effectively, with emphasis on output volume, quality, and timeliness (Kaur, 2016).

Employee productivity is further described as the efficiency with which an employee transforms inputs such as time, effort, and skills into useful outputs (Heathfield, 2021). Similarly, Boundless Management (2020) defines employee productivity as the value of goods or services produced per unit of labor input, highlighting the conversion of time and effort into valuable outcomes. Samson and Daft (2021) also conceptualize employee productivity as the quantity of output generated by an employee within a specified time period. In the same vein, Yadav and Dabhade (2022) view employee productivity as the measurable rate at which an employee produces goods or services. The Society for Human Resource Management (2022) reinforces this perspective by defining employee productivity as the degree to which employees efficiently convert inputs—such as time, effort, and resources—into valuable organizational outputs.

Anecdotal evidence revealed a significant correlation between comprehensive training initiatives and improvement in service delivery metrics within Nigeria Public service Adetayo et.al (2022). Howbeit, as effective as training is, there are encumbrances in the execution, implementation and overall application of it. Government invested huge substantial resources in training programs, workshop, and capacity building initiatives. Despite these efforts, public service struggles with constraints vis-a-vis inefficiency, delay, poor service delivery, low training elasticity, poor compensation benefits, unsupported leadership, bureaucracies, and under-utilization of human resources. In every organisation human resource is the most valuable, reliable asset, the ultimate basis for manpower development if only when intellectually and emotionally trained; howbeit, persistent underperformance highlight critical gap in understanding the relationship between acquired skills and performance outcomes. Hence, this paper x-rays the application of skills and performance outcomes in the public service: Rethinking elasticity dynamics.

Conceptual framework

A. The Nexus between Skills deficit and Performance Management in Nigeria public service

The Nigerian government has acknowledged the importance of workforce development through initiatives such as the Public Service Reform Program and the establishment of various training institutions. These initiatives reflect an understanding that equipping employees with necessary skills and knowledge is vital for enhancing the operational efficiency of public service. However, despite these various training institutions, there are deficiencies reflecting in the service delivery of employees. One of it is skill gap- but first what is a skill; it is the translation of Hebrew word

"Sakal" (Pronounced Saw-kal) which means expertise or special abilities to perform tasks (Mitee and Numbere, 2008). Skill is an observable behavior that is acquired through education, training, or experience; while skill gap is between the skills an employee has and the skills he or she actually needs to perform a job. Skills gaps vary depending on the job in question and the types of skills required for the job. For entry-level employees it is a different ball game compared to current employees in the workforce.

To manage performance of current employees, employers carried out performance appraisal system (PAS). This system aligns with organisational objectives with employees' performance targets, measures, competencies, development plans and fair assessment, recognition and reward for the delivery of result. It is a strategic tool for transforming talent into sustainable competitive advantage (Tavares and Vas, 2025). Employers' measures performance based on supply and demand; supply of performance information and demand of performance will not automatically adjust to each other, hence incorporation assures the link between both. This measurement has played a pivotal role in reform initiatives. Performance measurement possesses the dialectic nature of knowledge creation; the more employees know, the more they become aware of what they did not know. Performance measurement initiative happens as a result of skill-gap among workers competence, hence employers embarked on performance appraisal to know the shortage in skill deficit among employees; and these measurement criteria includes: prioritizing, indicator selection, data collection, analysis and reporting.

B. Skill Elasticity and Productivity in Public Service Organizations

Elasticity, a concept borrowed from economics, refers to the responsiveness of one variable in respect to changes in another. Relatively to public service, it provides useful lens in examining how employees' performance reacts to varying levels of skill application. Unlike linear models, elasticity dynamics accounts for non-uniformity and contextual dependency in outcomes. Key criteria includes:

1. **Threshold effects:** Certain minimum conditions—such as supportive management, adequate resources, or aligned tasks—must exist before skills effectively impact performance. Without these, even highly trained employees may fail to produce meaningful results.
2. **Diminishing returns:** Beyond a certain point, additional training or skill acquisition produces marginal improvements unless accompanied by organizational support. This explains why repeated capacity-building initiatives often fail to yield proportional performance gains.
3. **Context sensitivity:** The same level of skill application can produce vastly different outcomes depending on institutional culture, leadership, and employee motivation.

Collaboratively, scholars have identified that investment in skills training can result in the development of firm-specific skills that can boost individual and organizational performance leading to increased productivity and earnings (Garcia, 2005; Riley et al., 2017). From economic perspective, International Labour Organization conceptualizes productivity as the ratio between outputs and the inputs of resources utilized in the production process (Egbon-Charles et al, 2024 cited Kato, 2016). Conversely, it is seen as the efficient conversion of inputs such as time, effort, and skills into valuable outputs; a function of individual capability and institutional elasticity (Kwon, 2019; Arciniega et al., 2021; Yoo et al., 2022).

C. Digital Skills, Innovation, and Elastic Performance Gains for sustainability

The recent advent of new technologies, such as artificial intelligence, has drastically transformed the nature of work in organizations (Cerullo, 2023). The emergence of modern technologies and evolving public expectations necessitates a reassessment of traditional training methodologies. The integration of innovative training methods, such as e-learning and on-the-job training, has demonstrated enhanced learning outcomes and adaptability among public servants (Olaoye et al., 2023). It is revealed that digital technology increases innovation potential, creates opportunities for entrepreneurship and contribute positively to the improvement of innovation competitiveness (Bresciani et al., 2018; Brock and Von Wangenheim, 2019; Li et al., 2020, Martínez-Caro et al., 2020;Usai et al., 2021,Wang et al., 2022). Public service employees have long focused on traditional areas like financial management, leadership development, and project management; as they are also referred to as digital immigrants unlike employees known as digital natives-they have firm grasp of the nitty gritty of the application and use of digital technologies. Government as employer of labour must ensure that innovation is of primary concern among all levels of employees(natives and immigrants) as it can contribute to higher competitiveness; generate new ideas and promoting the achievement of sustainable development (Rindasu et al, 2023). The diagram below is a modified adapted model of digital transformation as guide for administrators, supervisors and trainers as well;

Fig 1.0: Adapted version of Digital Transformation Model

D. Factors Affecting the Effective Application of Skills among Employees'

The following are factors affecting effective application of skills among employees in the Public service. They are as follows:

1. Work Design and Task Meaningfulness

Work design significantly influences the extent to which employees are able to apply their acquired skills in the public service. Compared to the private sector, public sector work is often characterized by limited task complexity, rigid routines, and weak performance differentiation, which can constrain opportunities for skill utilization. When jobs are narrowly defined and lack challenge, employees are less motivated to deploy existing competencies or invest in acquiring new ones. For skills to be effectively applied, management must intentionally design work that aligns task complexity with employee capabilities. This includes assigning responsibilities that are meaningful, intellectually engaging, and commensurate with the quality and sensitivity of the work involved (Chen, 2024). Well-designed jobs enable employees to recognize the significance of their

contributions, understand how their efforts translate into outcomes, and perceive the broader value of their work within the organization. Such task clarity and meaningfulness foster intrinsic motivation, encouraging employees to actively apply and refine their skills. In turn, this enhances performance, supports continuous learning, and strengthens overall organizational effectiveness in the public service.

2. Basic Compensation and Employment Benefits

Basic compensation and employment benefits are fundamental determinants of how effectively employees apply their skills in the workplace. At the point of entry into the labour market, employees are expected to demonstrate competence-based skills that justify their recruitment and contribute to organizational goals. However, when compensation and benefits do not correspond with the level of effort, efficiency, and expertise supplied by employees, motivation to fully apply these skills is significantly weakened. This mismatch reduces performance incentives and undermines overall organizational achievement.

Compensation occupies a central position in employment relations, serving not only as economic reward but a signal of value-recognition and fairness. The International Labour Organization's Decent Work Agenda situates compensation and benefits within four interrelated pillars: standards and rights at work, including fair wages and remuneration; employment creation and enterprise development; social protection for all; and social dialogue. These pillars are embedded in international labour conventions and therefore constitute binding labour standards for ratifying states.

When organizations like public service compromise any of these pillars—through inadequate pay, weak social protection, or exclusion from dialogue—employee commitment and morale decline. As a result, skills application becomes constrained and performance outcomes turn inelastic, meaning that increases in skills or effort do not translate into proportional improvements in productivity or results.

3. Personal Commitment and Attitudinal Orientation

Personal commitment plays a critical role in determining how acquired skills are applied. In the Nigeria public service, routine job structures and guaranteed remuneration have fostered a culture of complacency, where employees rely on past competencies and assume that unchanged performance expectations will persist. However, the world of work is rapidly evolving, driven largely by digitalization and changing organizational demands. Where employees exhibit low commitment and weak work ethic—often reinforced by perceptions of job security regardless of output—the practical application of skills becomes limited, resulting in slow work processes and diminished institutional performance. This contrasts sharply with environments where personal responsibility and performance accountability are emphasized.

Conversely, employees who demonstrate commitment, adaptability, and a positive attitude toward their roles are more inclined to continuously apply and update their skills. Such individuals actively seek new knowledge, embrace emerging technologies, and remain competitive in the workforce. This sustained commitment enhances effective skill utilization, leading to improved productivity, innovation, and higher performance outcomes.

Other factors include; Customers, Economy, political (Legislative factor)

Conclusion

Persistent underperformance is not primarily a consequence of insufficient skills but ineffective application of skills within the workplace. Understanding how application of skills correlates with performance provides valuable insights for human resource planning not only within public service

but cut across other service sectors. Using elasticity dynamics as a conceptual lens, this paper demonstrates that performance responsiveness to skills is non-linear, context-dependent, and influenced by institutional and environmental factors. Addressing this lacuna requires a shift from traditional training-focused approaches to strategic skill utilization, adaptive management, and supportive institutional environments. To this end, when employees applied the skills they have learnt and gained, it makes them improve more on their performance both psychologically, physically, and socially.

Recommendations

The researcher made the following recommendations for guide to administrators, policy holders, HR expert and educational institutions. They are;

1. Establish a structure for monitoring, supervision and evaluating training programmes to enhance continuous learning among employees.
2. Adopting adaptive work-design and human resource interventions based on institutional needs and public service rules.
3. Institutionalizing digital innovation and providing adequate technological infrastructure. This will enhance efficiency, innovation, service delivery, and sustainable performance.
4. Transparent and performance-based compensation frameworks should be implemented to ensure fairness in employee remuneration. Aligning pay with workload, competence, and productivity will enhance motivation and overall performance.

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